

“The role of school in expanding the worldview of young adults”

Aitbayeva Gulchehra Kuanishbay qizi

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign [Languages](#)

aytbayevagulchehra24@gmail.com

Scientific supervisor: **Zubaydova Nilufar Nematullayevna**

Abstract: Expanding the worldview of young adults is important for their future personal and professional development. The school is the main social institution in shaping the outlook of young people. This article analyzes how school affects the intellectual, moral, cultural and social development of young people. Also, the role of teachers and educational programs, family and school cooperation in the educational process is analyzed in the formation of the intellectual and moral image of young people. The article gives recommendations for increasing the influence of school and its effectiveness in the formation of the worldview of young people.

Keywords: Youth, outlook, school, upbringing, education, teacher, ethics, culture, family, personality.

Main part

The outlook of young people is one of the most important factors in human life. Especially, the worldview of young adults has a great influence on what path they will choose in the future, what kind of person they will become and what place they will occupy in society. The role of the school in this process is of particular importance, because the majority of young people spend most of their time in this institution. The school functions not only as an educational institution, but also as an educational institution. This is an important factor in expanding the worldview of young people.

The first task of the school in shaping the outlook of young people is to influence their intellectual development. Through the curriculum, students are given in-depth knowledge of subjects, which helps them to look at life in a broader way. In the process of mastering science, young people acquire different worldviews and learn to search for the truth based on scientific knowledge. Educational programs should not be limited to imparting knowledge, but they should also develop critical thinking skills of young people. Critical thinking, in turn, expands the worldview of young people, teaches them to actively respond to various social, cultural and scientific issues.

Also, the school plays a big role in forming the moral outlook of students. Moral education helps all students in the school to understand their personal responsibility, to feel their place and importance in society. The role of teachers in this process is incomparable. They form healthy social values in them through their personal example, love and attention shown to students. A good teacher not only increases the interest of young people in learning, but also forms a responsible attitude towards society in them.

Another important task of the school is cultural and social development of young people. In the educational process, students are taught not only scientific knowledge, but also cultural values, traditions and customs. Through this, they understand their national culture more deeply and learn to respect other nationalities and cultures. In this way, the outlook of young people expands and they learn to be open to the world. The role of the school in this process is to educate students not only as individuals with knowledge, but also as people with high spirituality and cultural image.

Cooperation between family and school is also very important here. The educational process is not limited to school. The family is also an integral part of the educational process. Effective cooperation between parents and teachers has a positive effect on the development of young people. Parents need to take into account the interests and needs of their children and give them the right direction. The school participates in this process as a scientific and moral guiding institution. The school is especially important in developing the moral worldview of its students, in understanding their place in society. One of the main goals of the school is to educate students on the basis of national and universal values, to form a civic position in them. In the process of social education of the school, young people realize the need to actively participate in their society. They also learn to correctly assess their place in society, and this affects their personal development and future life choices.

The success of the school in the educational process largely depends on the qualifications and pedagogical approaches of the teachers. A good teacher makes his lessons interesting and informative, arouses students' interest and encourages them to expand their knowledge. At the same time, the use of modern educational technologies helps to make the educational process effective. In schools, it is necessary to take into account the individual abilities of students, to give them the opportunity to develop within their abilities and interests. Through this, young people's outlook will expand and they will confidently step into their future. School

serves as the main foundation in the future life of young people. It not only gives knowledge, but also education. During the school process, students get knowledge in various fields, and through this knowledge, they expand their worldview. Moral, social and cultural values also play an important role in the educational process of the school. Also, the effectiveness of cooperation between family and school is of great importance.

In short, school has a great role in expanding the worldview of young adults. The school affects their intellectual, moral, cultural and social development and educates them to be active and responsible individuals in society. The qualifications of teachers, the quality of educational programs and the effectiveness of cooperation with parents determine the success of the school in this process. Therefore, it is necessary to fully use the opportunities of the school in expanding the worldview of young people and to improve this process in accordance with the requirements of the time.

Conclusion

The influence of school in expanding the worldview of young adults is very important. The school greatly contributes to their intellectual, moral, cultural and social development. The school education system is not limited to enriching young people only with scientific knowledge, but also forms them as useful individuals for society. The influence of the school is strengthened through the individual approach of teachers, proper organization of the educational process and strong cooperation with the family. The expansion of young people's worldview serves as a foundation for their future life choices and personal development. Therefore, it is necessary to ensure that the school plays a leading role in the educational and educational process and to enrich it with modern educational technologies in order to educate the future generation as a comprehensively developed person.

The list of literature:

1. Olimov N. A. "Yoshlar dunyoqarashini shakllantirishda ta'lim va tarbiyaning o'rni." Toshkent: O'zbekiston Fanlar Akademiyasi nashriyoti, 2018. – 320 p.
2. Karimova S. T. "Maktab tizimida axloqiy tarbiya: nazariya va amaliyot." Toshkent: Ilm Ziyo nashriyoti, 2020. – 250 p.
3. R. A Utkurovich, R. G Utkurovna. "Teaching English Language To Primary Level Pupils At School" Ijodkor O'qituvchi 3 (36), 103-105, 2024

4. Xudoyqulov M. R. "O'quvchilarni ijtimoiy tarbiyalashda o'qituvchilarning roli." Samarqand: Ma'rifat nashriyoti, 2019. – 180 p.
5. Tursunova G. K. "Milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiya berish usullari." Toshkent: Yangi asr avlodi nashriyoti, 2021. – 275 p.
6. Yuldoshev A. O. "Yoshlarning intellektual rivojlanishida maktab va oila hamkorligi." Buxoro: Sharq nashriyoti, 2017. – 230 p.
7. Shokhista, R. (2023). The Significance Of Emphasizing Communicative Competence As The Foundation For Teaching Listening And Speaking Skills Rustamova Shokhista Sharifovna. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 25-28.
8. Rustamova, S. S. (2023, January). The Importance Of Speaking Activities In Teaching English. In International Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 357-361).
9. Sharifovna, R. S. (2022). Teaching Spoken English To Upper Class Pupils. Confrencea, 6(6), 87-89.
10. Sharifovna, R. S. (2022). Class Size And The Learning-Teaching Process In Upper Classes. Journal of new century innovations, 14(1), 86-98.
11. Sharipovna, R. S. Peculiarities Of Teaching English In Secondary Schools In Uzbekistan. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, (2), 1-5.
12. Suleymanova, N. M. (2020). On The Nominative Nature Of The Sentence. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 307-309.
13. Сулейманова, Н. М. (2017). Номинативный аспект речевого процесса. In Humanities and Social Sciences in Europe: Achievements and Perspectives (pp. 76-82).
14. Suleymanova, N. M., & Idiyev, A. R. O. G. L. (2021). Gapping Nominativ Aspekti Va Uning Kommunikativ Jarayoni Haqida. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(12), 805-809.
15. Сулейманова, Н. М., & Абдуллаева, Л. Т. (2017). Имманентный характер синергетических свойств единиц языковой системы. In Инновации В Современном Языковом Образовании (pp. 61-65).
16. Ikrambayevna, S. D. (2024). Classification of Functions of Communicative Strategy and Tactics in Political Communication. Miasto Przyszłości, 50, 548-553.
17. Sattarova, D. (2024). Siyosiy Muloqotning Pragmatik Aspektlari. Tamaddun Nuri Jurnal, 5(56), 380-383.

18. Axmedova, D., & Zarmaskhonov, S. (2024, February). Exploring Global Perspectives In Language Teaching And Learning. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 205-207).
19. Sattarova, D. (2024, January). Siyosiy Notqlikning Milliy Madaniy Va Lisoniy Tahlili (O'zbekiston Respublikasi Birinchi Prezidenti Ia Karimov Nutqlari Asosida). In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 5-7).
20. Makhmudova, G. N., & Gulomova, N. F. (2023). Unlocking the potential of the digital economy in the EAEU countries: identifying and overcoming obstacles. *π-Economy*, 16 (4), 7–25. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18721/JE.16401>.
21. Гуломова, Н. (2022). Основные компоненты развития «умного» туризма в регионах. Направления развития благоприятной бизнес-среды в условиях цифровизации экономики, 1(01), 63-67.
22. Makhmudova, G., Gulomova, N., & Mirzaev, D. (2022). Legal aspects of cryptocurrency and blockchain technologies: Uzbekistan and foreign experience.
23. Jumayeva, M. (2022). Analysis Of The Views Of Scientists Of The Renaissance, Based On A Unique Approach To Pedagogy And Education And Upbringing. *Science and Innovation*, 1(5), 26-29.
24. Sattarova, D. (2023). Komunikativ Diskursning Tadqiqot Ob'yekti. *Молодые ученые*, 1(22), 41-43.
25. Ikramboyevna, A. D., & Ikramboyevna, S. D. (2023). The Ways of Forming Secondary Nomination in Uzbek Language and Its Impact on Linguistics.